

Migration Process in Republic of Türkiye: Changes in Push and Pull Factors Over Time

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Abstract

During the migration process, people change their current places of residence to migrate to other locations to improve their life quality and benefit from various social and economic advantages. This migration process generally occurs from underdeveloped regions to more developed and advanced regions. Considering the reality of intercity migration in Türkiye, big cities that seem to have pull factors have always been one of the most important directions for migration. At the same time, small cities also possess some push factors. These factors have changed over time, and people migrate to different places during the intercity migrations as consequences of push and pull factors. In this paper, the historical changes of the factors affecting migration in Türkiye will be examined. Theoretical aspects of migration process, history of intercity migrations and their push and pull factors, fundamental motivations and sociological factors and consequences of migration process will be analysed. Eventually, a comparative analysis of intercity migration according to the different periods will be presented.

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Türkiye Cumhuriyeti'nde Göç Süreci: İtici ve Çekici Faktörlerin Zaman İçindeki Değişimleri

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Özet

Göç sürecinde bireyler, yaşam kalitelerini artırmak ve çeşitli sosyal ile ekonomik avantajlardan yararlanmak amacıyla mevcut yerleşim alanlarını değiştirerek farklı bölgelere göç etmektedir. Bu süreç genellikle az gelişmiş bölgelerden daha gelişmiş ve ileri bölgelere doğru gerçekleşmektedir. Türkiye'deki iller arası göç gerçeği dikkate alındığında, çekici faktörlere sahip büyük kentler her zaman göçün en önemli yönelim alanlarından biri olmuştur. Bununla birlikte, küçük kentler de belirli itici faktörler barındırmaktadır. Zaman içerisinde bu faktörler değişmiş; itici ve çekici unsurların bir sonucu olarak insanlar iller arası göç kapsamında farklı yönlerde hareket etmiştir. Bu çalışmada, Türkiye'de göçü etkileyen faktörlerin tarihsel değişimi incelenecektir. Göç sürecinin kuramsal çerçevesi, iller arası göçlerin tarihsel gelişimi ve bu göçlere etki eden itici ve çekici faktörler, temel motivasyonlar ile sosyolojik etkenler ve göç sürecinin sonuçları ele alınacaktır. Son olarak, farklı dönemlere göre iller arası göçün karşılaştırmalı bir analizi sunulacaktır.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Throughout history, people have migrated from their home regions to other regions, settled and established their lives there. While it seems difficult to leave the places where they were born and that they are accustomed to, the prospect of settling in a better location and enjoying a better standard of living has motivated them to migrate. While the migration process remains uncertain until its completion, there are several underlying factors that motivate people to migrate and main motivation behind the migration is to move from a small and underdeveloped place to a big and developed place. The advantages that big cities have pull people who live in the small cities to them. When considering these advantages, migration route turns to big cities.

There is a remarkable relation between human development and human mobility and this relation has become an interesting discussion point in academia. Classically, international migration seems to be influenced by financial differences in regions and regional development. It has been an important discussion point in media and policy. The reasons such as underdevelopment, poverty and conflict are perceived as the most important drivers of the migration from poor countries to the rich countries, or, rural to the urban places for internal migration in developing countries (de Haas & Franzen, 2018, p. 4). During the migration, there is an alteration of the place and migration influences the population. In this regard, population of the places that are emigrated decrease while population of the immigrated places increase. Internal migrations happen within the same place while international migrations happen in between two different countries. Nowadays, there are advantageous and disadvantageous sides of migration that developments in transportation increases the movements of the individuals, but, it also enables illegal border crossings (Sharlamanov, 2019, p. 313-314).

In general, the concept of migration is the process of people migrating from their current location to another region and continuing their lives there. This involves not only changing the region where a person was born, raised and spent their lives, but also, reshaping one's culture, influencing it from the culture of the destination, and bringing one's own culture to the destination (Ak, 2021, p. 1749). In this sense, there is a sociological effect of the migration too. Adaptation to the norms of the different places and presenting one's own norms in the place where is migrated happens. Migration is primarily between urban and rural areas. Migration between neighborhoods and districts, short-term migrations and travel are not considered migration. Internal migration has both positive and negative consequences. It is not free-will migration, but rather directed migration. These migrations are movements resulting from state decisions. Technological advancements and new production trends are accelerating rural-urban migration. With urbanization, people integrate; that is, they blend with larger population (Es & Ateş, 2010, p. 209, 211-212, 214).

While, people migrated to cities to participate in industrial production, urbanization also led to inter-sectoral labor transfers. This surplus population also shifted to the service sector, creating

hidden unemployment. Those migrating from rural areas to cities had to work in hard jobs. This, in turn, led to psychological pressure and unhappiness, as they were unable to achieve a certain level of economic standard, leading to feelings of social exclusion (Yılmaz, 2009, s. 29-30).

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF MIGRATION CONCEPT

There have been times when different groups of people have left their home regions for different reasons and moved to other regions. Also, it is not absolute to assume that societies have never migrated. Small-scale migrations within regions have always happened. Small-scale internal migrations have played a significant role in shaping local cultures. According to Altunok, internal migration from rural areas to cities began with the Industrial Revolution. This migration trend continued after World War II. Particularly after countries gained their independence after the war, there was a flow of workers from rural areas to large cities as they took steps toward industrialization. While urbanization accelerated and population density began to increase in large cities, rural areas experienced a loss of labor and a decline in the youth population. While the reasons for internal migration in developing countries are unbalanced land distribution, unemployment, and income disparities, in developed countries, the search for prosperity and the desire to raise living standards are primary drivers (Altunok, 2021, s. 15).

Ravenstein has conducted significant research on migration and discussed its various dimensions. According to Ravenstein, people migrate for specific reasons, and there are specific immigration laws. In his work, *Laws of Migration*, he lists the principles of immigration law as follows:

- 1) Migration and distance,
- 2) Migration and its steps,
- 3) The process of dispersal and absorption,
- 4) Migration chains,
- 5) Direct migration,
- 6) Differences between rural and urban residents,
- 7) Differences between men and women (Ravenstein, 1885, p. 198-199).

Ravenstein addressed the fundamental approaches to migration theory and how migration occurs and begins. However, others have examined migration theory from different perspectives. Everett Lee examined the reasons for the migration process. According to Lee, people migrate for four reasons:

- 1) Factors related to the place of residence,
- 2) Factors related to the intended destination,
- 3) Obstacles that interfere with work,
- 4) Individual factors (Lee, 1966, p. 50).

Furthermore, migration has push and pull characteristics, depending on the reasons mentioned above. Push factors are negative factors that drive people away from their current locations. Examples include environmental degradation, heavy traffic, difficulties accessing public services, housing shortages, environmental disasters, security concerns, and so on. These factors are called push factors. Pull factors, on the other hand, are positive factors that motivate people to live and continue their lives in a particular location. For example, ease of access to public services, a safe environment, low or affordable costs of living, abundant job opportunities, and the absence of infrastructure problems are all examples of pull factors (Adıgüzel, 2024, s. 47).

There are other international, contemporary approaches to migration. Migration system helps us to clarify the formal assessments and relationship between different actors which are linked over time and whether response cycles are sustaining or weakening the connections. Internal factors that are combining the elements and external factors which are parts of the wider environment are important to understand in migration system perspective. Grey literature among different research fields approaches system thinking as a tool to improve the clarity, predictability and good expectancy. Migration process is complex and it is related to the societal changes. International migration evolved over the years led by globalization and it created an environment of interconnectedness and interdependency. The new appearance of the migration with the new contemporary challenges makes it hard to contribute to the migration governance. The term migration governance doesn't only address the governmental level of migration management but it goes deeper to the public and private actors. Therefore, civil society, trade unions etc. are seen as competent and relevant actors in migration governance as well as national authorities. From this perspective, system thinking is a practical method to understand the migration process (Tagliacozza et al., 2024, p. 1100, 1104-1105).

In contemporary approaches, also the globalization factor, as the first dimension of migration, is changing the understanding about how international migration functions. There are obstacles to explain the current trends of the migration. It is dealing with two dilemmas that providing of the manpower to the developed economies and how to evolve it and addressing of the national and supranational institutions to the actual topics in migration. As states are becoming more restrictive towards migration movements, they tend to acknowledge temporary migration. The question is that whether neoliberal policies of free circulation and the new protectionist model of flexibility contradicts. The second dimension is about rights of migrants. Yet, it remains to be ideologically abstract and the standards that they live in are not sufficiently focused to put into practice (Piché, 2013, p. 157, 158).

All in all, the approaches and theories of migration has always been dynamic and the reality of the migration is an ongoing process so far. The factors that influenced this process in each era and in each geography showed that the factors that are causing the migration movements affected by different reasons. Therefore, the periodical analysis of the fact is also crucial to conceptualize the migration reasons and dynamics.

3. ANALYSIS OF MIGRATION ACCORDING TO THE PERIODS

Considering all the factors, there are many factors that trigger the migration in Türkiye. People have migrated from one region to another for different reasons in Türkiye history. These population movements has led to various impacts. People have left the cities and regions where they were born and raised, opting for more developed cities and regions with more job opportunities. Push factors in rural areas have driven people to these regions. However, over time, due to factors such as the increasing population influx to the cities and inability of cities to accommodate this infrastructure, push factors have also emerged in cities. In fact, this has led to new movements, such as reverse migration trends, emerging today.

Adıgüzel observed that there are different push and pull factors in all stages and divided the historical development of rural-urban migration in Turkish history after Republic period into 3 different periods:

- 1923 – 1950,
- 1950 – 1980 period,
- Post-1980 period (Adıgüzel, 2024, s. 42-46).

In this part, the migration periods will be analyzed in 4 different periods. The impact of the events in the history of Republic and developments in international politics reflected the migration phases in Türkiye during these periods. The influence of different factors became evident in each period. While there were occasional differences, the impact of certain factors on migration remained consistent throughout each period.

3.1. 1923 to 1950 Migration Period

Since the founding of the Republic of Türkiye, the remaining population had diminished following the World War I and War of Independence. Furthermore, migrations from war-affected regions to major cities occurred for security reasons.

After the proclamation of the Republic, uprisings occurred and these movements constituted security concerns in the country. Sheikh Said Rebellion and others led to internal migrations. In this context, security issues were the push factors, particularly in small, war-affected regions, while the primary pull factors for emigrated regions was their security and protection. Saygın makes an analysis that if the reasons for the outbreak of these rebellions are considered, it is striking that the rebellions originated in the Eastern regions due to both geographical location of the region and the fact that the state authority was not fully realized (Saygın, 2022, s. 13). After the Turkish War of Independence, to maintain the control in the regions were hard at the beginning. Lack of financial conditions and reduction of human power factors were obstacles to overcome the issues of the newly

established state. Also, political changes that did not satisfy some groups which were opposing to the republican order and secularism led these happenings.

Even if there was no significant population movement during this period, it's possible to say that both forced migration and preventive measures were taken. During this period, 'the peasant is the master of the nation' perspective is adopted by governments. So, the motivations of the policies in this period were to reduce and prevent migrations. Law No. 1097, dated June 10, 1927, 'On the Transfer of Certain Persons from the Eastern Region to the Western Provinces' was enacted. Subsequently, Law No. 2510 on Settlement expanded the current government's authority in this regard. Thus, the population in the East was forced to migrate to the West through forced migration practices (Altunok, 2021, p. 41-43). They were aimed at distributing the population more evenly across the regions.

Although Türkiye did not participate in World War II, the conscription of large numbers of people into military service resulted in a decrease in the agricultural workforce and a decline in agricultural production. At the same time, the imposition of taxes on farmers to cope with the difficult economic conditions at the time further exacerbated the already difficult conditions of farmers (Kaya vd., 2015, p. 92). The prolonged military service of men in rural areas, resulting in decline in agricultural production in these regions, was a factor pushing people to big cities. Also, as mechanization in agriculture reduced number of people working in agriculture, people began migrating to big cities. Moreover, people wanted to profit the services and more job opportunities offered by the big cities.

In this regard, the lack of labor in agriculture, early uprisings, government-controlled migration policies and lack of services in small cities are main push factors, while the abundance of these resources and the capacity to address the needs of citizens in big cities, safety and job opportunities are the pull factors of this period. Even if full-scale internal migration did not occur during this period, it influenced future migrations to big cities in Türkiye.

3.2. 1950 to 1980 Migration Period

Between 1950 and 1970, internal migration accelerated. Türkiye's rapid urbanization process began during the Democrat Party's reign, which came to power following the 1950 elections. Primary objective of the Democrat Party was to strengthen the agricultural sector, not the industrial sector (Adıgüzel, 2024, s. 43). During the Democrat Party era, there were initiatives for mechanization in Türkiye. Tractors and combine harvesters were imported with Marshall aid. These developments reduced the need for labor in agriculture. This factor led to the migration of unemployed labor in agricultural sector to big cities. Increased bus service made transportation easier. For people living in other regions, access to big cities became less of a hassle (Özer, 2014, p. 77). The fact that big cities housed the majority of industry became a popular attraction for people. Unqualified and poorly educated young people migrating to cities have become a significant labor force for the industrial

and service sectors. In addition to temporary seasonal agricultural workers, people from rural areas started migrating to cities permanently (Altunok, 2021, s. 45).

All these factors combined led to a natural increase in the population of big cities. This increase also brought about some negative consequences. As housing capacity couldn't accommodate the incoming population, illegal construction, or slums, began to emerge. The development of slums resulted in irregular urban development, resulting in unplanned urbanization. Law No. 775 on Slums, which became law in 1966, was enacted during this period. The drafters of the law began with the definition of slum. The following four principles are considered the true causes of slum formation: 1) It is illegal, 2) It is built on someone else's land, 3) It is unauthorized structure, 4) It is unlicensed (illegal) from the municipality (Çakır, 2011, s. 217).

Other reasons for migration include persistence of the aga and tribal systems in Eastern and Southeastern Anatolia, coupled with the scarcity of land. The majority of land owned by landlords created economic hardship for the people. The diversification of production coordination and the activities of large landowners led to a necessary transformation in the village's social structure, along with the traditional relations between villagers and landowner. It created an insecure atmosphere in villages. This process resulted in the forced expulsion of villagers. The traditional sharecropping status remained largely dependent on the landowner. In addition to economic factors, the atmosphere of insecurity in the village also became a factor triggering rural-urban migration (Altunok, 2021, s. 45-46). Within this framework, security-related factors such as blood feuds also influenced migration. The idea that families would be safer and more peaceful in big cities was a pull factor. Given these conditions, access to public services in rural areas was limited. The families migrating to big cities gradually became urban dwellers, taking other family members and relatives with them over time.

During this period, economic and social transformations began in big cities. While urbanization accelerated, the intensity of migration created the problem of slums. The rural population gradually declined, and village culture was reflected in urban culture. While big cities in the West grew economically, Anatolian cities lagged behind, creating regional inequalities. The rural population began aging gradually and losing the young population. When examining the push and pull factors of migration during this period, the primary push factors were unemployment, poverty, inflation, land scarcity, security, and limited public services. Pull factors included improved public services, greater job opportunities and industrialization. Ultimately, under the influence of these factors, big cities took their first steps towards becoming megacities. At the same time, the push and pull factors of migration shifted due to the social and political problems encountered during and after this period.

3.3. 1980 to 2000's Migration Period

Migration in Türkiye continued to increase from the 1980's to the 2000's. Political, social, and financial changes occurred in Türkiye in the 1980's. The military seized power with the September 12, 1980 coup. When examined in this context, neoliberal policies began to be implemented within the scope of the January 24 Decisions. These years were a period of free market dominance in the economy, intense privatization, and the addition of individual liberalization and freedoms. Another notable urbanization element was the improved quality of social services such as education, transportation, and healthcare in cities (Adıgüzel, 2024, s. 45). These free market initiatives and neoliberal policies influenced migration and led to changes in sectors. Public investments began to decline, and privatizations were implemented in place of them, taking steps consistent with the policies of the time.

Another factor that significantly impacted internal migration in Türkiye after 1980 was the decline of agriculture. With the 'adaptation policies' implemented in the 1980's, agricultural management began to dissolve from the bottom up, resulting in a shift in the functions of the relevant ministry's central and provincial organizations (Özdemir, 2012, p. 8). These developments led to insufficient focus on agriculture. The population in rural areas decreased; young people, in particular, began to migrate to big cities. In fact, from this perspective, migration has had negative consequences in both migrant-sending and migrant-receiving regions.

Additionally, there has been a massive migration from Eastern and Southeastern Anatolia to the big cities in Türkiye. This was due to terrorist activities and security concerns in these regions. The evacuation of villages due to security concerns reduced the rural population, and the population migrated to western regions, particularly to the bigger cities. Village raids and attacks by the PKK forced people to leave these areas. The evacuation of villages has reduced agriculture and livestock production in the region. Also, people lost their livestock, land, and homes. Lacking any means of support or work, the migrants suffered extreme poverty. The scarcity of the resources in the places they migrated to led to problems such as unemployment, unplanned urbanization, cultural conflict, and other problems in the cities (Çilmi, 2024, s. 171, 177).

Push factors during this period include terrorism and neglect of agriculture which accelerated the rural-urban migration. Pull factors include increased industrialization, increased job opportunities, improved transportation, and the further development of public services.

3.4. Contemporary Migration

Until 2000's, migration from rural to urban areas caused economic and social problems in urban areas, such as intense population pressure, unplanned urbanization, and the development of slums. These problems, which emerged in urban areas, accumulated over time and began to neg-

actively impact the attractiveness of cities. As cities began to be overwhelmed by push factors and efforts to prevent rural migration, rural areas began to become new magnets. Consequently, reverse migration has become a significant phenomenon in recent years (İslamoğlu vd., 2014, s. 69). There has been a shift in the perception of internal migration today. This shift has become particularly pronounced following the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic has brought remote working practices into our lives. By going beyond daily working practices and starting to work remotely, people have realized that they are not dependent on the city to sustain their lives and they have embraced the idea of 'longing to be in nature' by getting out of the stay-at-home psychology created by the pandemic (Kızıllhan vd., 2025, s. 628). During the COVID-19 period, the movements of the individual are restricted to decrease the danger of the pandemic. Also, migration is affected not only by restrictions but economic results of COVID-19 (Sirkeci et al., 2022, p. 2). According to Özlü Diniz, the negative conditions brought by the white-collar work environment, the reflection of these negativities on their family lives, and their desire for their children not to live such a life symbolize reverse migration as 'escape from the city' (Özlü Diniz & Arslan, 2022, p. 225). The significant rise in living standards in big cities has pushed people to settle in smaller areas where they can sustain their lives. This phenomenon can create a potential for growth in small cities. If local governments take steps to improve employment in these areas, these cities will develop remarkably. However, this growth is hampered by the risks of smaller areas having limited capacity and being unable to accommodate the incoming population. Considering these factors, reverse migration can be short-lived. As a result, people may return to big cities, especially because of the abundance of job opportunities.

The Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality implemented a reverse migration program. Logistics and financial support were provided to citizens for their return. The project is about redistribute Istanbul's population to other regions. People choose their own destinations, and the municipality provided the necessary assistance during this process (İslamoğlu vd., 2014, s. 80). The success of such projects depends on the proper guidance of municipalities. Directing people according to their professions, regional needs, and suitability for the region ensures successful reverse migration. By taking these conditions into account, municipalities can successfully retain migrants in their areas. Otherwise, reverse migration will fail and return to the big cities will accelerate. Also, the Village Return and Rehabilitation program, supported by the Ministry of Interior, is currently providing incentives for people to return their villages. The goal is to facilitate the return of citizens who have left their cities for security reasons and to maintain economic and social infrastructural development in the region (Ministry of Interior of the Republic of Türkiye, 2010). The Presidency's Annual Program has introduced several precautions for to not to lose rural population and reverse migration. According to this, objective of the reverse migration is to create a multifaceted economic structure in rural areas (Strategy and Budget Presidency of the Presidency of the Republic of Türkiye, 2025). By these programs, rural areas, villages and small cities will be revitalized.

Earthquake risk also a push factor driving people from big cities to smaller cities. The single most important criterion in the discussion of whether a natural event is a disaster is whether it affects society. In this respect, it's reasonable to call the February 6th earthquake a disaster, as all of Türkiye was affected both materially and spiritually by this disaster (Düzenli, 2024, s.77). In recent years, due to earthquakes in Marmara regions and the anticipation of a major earthquake in Istanbul, people have begun migrating to safe places where the risk of earthquake is low. This has led to a tendency to avoid densely populated areas. A devastating earthquake would negatively impact Istanbul. Therefore, areas with lower populations and lower earthquake risk are more popular today. The 2023 Kahramanmaraş earthquake, the 2025 Istanbul earthquake and 2025 Balıkesir earthquakes have frightened citizens. The Kahramanmaraş Earthquake was devastating, and the two other earthquakes resulted in the collapse of some vulnerable buildings and damage to others (Anadolu Agency, 2025; Kara-Kaşka, 2025). These risks have led to the initiation of an intensive urban renewal process in Türkiye. People are relocating from their old buildings to new ones a year after they are demolished by making agreements with contractors. The presence of older settlements and buildings in big cities has encouraged people to take precautions. There is a program called Half-On-Us Campaign. As part of the campaign, each residence is receiving an 875,000 TL grant, and 875,000 TL loan, and a 125,000 TL moving support. Citizens who benefit from the 1,875,000 TL financing provided by the Ministry for each residence can rebuild their homes with contractors. A 1,750,000 TL loan is available for each additional residence of the beneficiary. Loan repayments, which are interest-free for the first year, begin two years after the building permit is issued and are spread over a 10-year term (Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change of the Republic of Türkiye, n.d.).

Pull factors of big cities attract people, and over time, they have developed their own push factors. The more migration a region receives and the less infrastructure it has to accommodate, the more pronounced the push factors become. The growing population has brought with it various problems including, environmental pollution housing shortages, rising housing prices, traffic congestion, and increasing numbers of the slums.

4. CONCLUSION

While push and pull factors have varied throughout the history of Republic of Türkiye, certain factors have triggered inter-city migration movements in Türkiye. In each period, these factors have drawn people towards large and developed regions. In particular, the internal migration movement in Türkiye has always been from East to West. However, with the emergence of reverse migration trends, starting in the early 2000's, there has been a shift in this movement. People are finding smaller cities more suitable and livable. One of the main reasons for this is that citizens cannot afford the high living standards offered by the big cities. Factors such as overcrowding, environmental problems, lack of connection with nature, and earthquake risks have become the push factors for big cities.

A period-by-period analysis of Turkish history reveals that, in the early days of Türkiye's history, after the founding of the Republic and up until 1950, due to the destructive effects of war, insecurity in some regions and uprisings, led to migration to more secure areas. Mainly, migration was driven by government policies, economic hardship, lack of services and agricultural difficulties. In addition to these push factors, safety and the improved availability of public services, in big cities served as a pull factor for people. In the 1950's – 1970's, factors such as unemployment resulting from the reduced need for agricultural workers due to mechanization, falling incomes and unemployment in rural areas, regional inequalities, the aga system, land scarcity, blood feuds and the inadequacy of public services were the push factors of the period. During this period, the concentration of industry in big cities, ease of transportation, developed public services, and the availability of job opportunities in big cities were the pull factors that led people to migrate. In the migrations between 1980 and 2000, the impact of neoliberal policies on agricultural production, the rise of terrorism and security issues, the rise of regional economic inequalities, the rise of unemployment in rural areas, and the inadequacy of social services were the main push factors. During the same period, the development of the industrial and service sectors, the development of the public services, and the abundance of job opportunities were the main pull factors. After 2000 and today, there has been a shift in the context of push and pull factors. The push factors of big cities have increased. These difficulties have arisen because of the reason that the large population migrating to big cities. The direction of the migration shifted from big cities to smaller towns and rural areas. The push factors of this period were rising living costs, increasing housing shortages, traffic congestion, environmental pollution, earthquake risk, rising of slums and infrastructure problems in big cities. The main pull factors during this period were the lower cost of living in small cities, the lower earthquake risk, a quieter lifestyle, incentive programs for rural areas, and the ability to connect with nature.

Considering all factors, economics factors, especially industrial underdevelopment and unemployment, have always been push factors, while the inadequacy of public services has also been a prominent push factor. While the reasons for migration have varied throughout each era, people have always been more inclined to migrate due to economic conditions. In some periods, political and security reasons have also driven people to more developed and secure regions. Today, security reasons are aligned with the risks of natural disasters, particularly earthquakes. Initially, migration from rural areas to big cities continued to increase in other periods, eventually transforming into reverse migration. But, while the push factors of big cities have increased, their advantages, in other words, their pull factors, still make these regions desirable destinations for migration. While the push factors of big cities drive people to rural areas and smaller towns, if comprehensive policies are not implemented in these cities, the push factors of these regions will prevail, and the return to big cities will begin. Today, municipalities must have the infrastructure to adequately accommodate this population and, by increasing their cooperation, successfully manage reverse migration. This fact will gradually reduce the push factors for both big and small cities.

Based on these findings, policymakers can use this study to prevent negative impacts and consequences of intercity migration in Türkiye. Analyzing of these facts about the migration will allow individuals to grasp the historical development and future expectancies about the internal migration movements. Therefore, the trends and evolving push and pull factors in migration process of Türkiye is an important guideline for policy-makers and researchers to create projects and implement these projects as part of the migration policies.

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GENİŞLETİLMİŞ TÜRKÇE ÖZET

Göç sürecinde insanlar, yaşam kalitelerini iyileştirmek ve çeşitli sosyal ve ekonomik avantajlardan yararlanmak için mevcut ve ikamet ettikleri bölgeleri değiştirerek başka yerlere göç ederler. Uluslararası göçlerde hareketlenmeler genellikle Doğu'dan Batı'ya doğru gerçekleşir. Göç olgusu genellikle ülkeler ve bölgeler arası gerçekleşiyor olsa da, göç hareketlerinin şehirlerarası hareketliliği de vardır. Bu bağlamda, Türkiye'de şehirlerarası göçler görülmektedir. Türkiye'deki şehirler arası göçler incelendiği zaman, göçün gerçekleştiği yön Türkiye'de genellikle Doğu bölgelerinden Batı bölgelerine doğru gerçekleşmiştir. Günümüzde Türkiye'de tersine göç politikaları ve trendlerinin ortaya çıkmasıyla, ayrıca gelişmiş bölgelerin itici faktörlerinin artmasıyla da, insanlar küçük şehirlere ve daha az gelişmiş bölgelere doğru göç etmeye başlamıştır. Bu olaylar insanların göç alışkanlığını ve algısını tekrardan şekillendirmiştir.

Türkiye'de Cumhuriyet'in ilanından sonra takip eden dönemlerde meydana gelen göçlerin arka planında çeşitli ekonomik, siyasi, sosyal, ve çevresel sebepler yatmaktadır ve bu sebepleri tetikleyen toplumsal ve uluslararası olaylar da olmuştur. Bazı dönemlerde göçü oluşturan faktörlerde benzerlikler görülürken, her dönemde meydana gelen farklı olaylarla, itici ve çekici faktörlerin çeşitlendiği de olmuştur. Bu bakımdan göçü tetikleyen esas faktörler bazı dönemlerde benzer gibi görünse de, dönemin şartlarına göre farklılık göstermişlerdir. Göç süreci genellikle az gelişmiş bölgelerden daha gelişmiş ve ileri seviyede olan bölgelere doğru gerçekleşir. Bununla beraber göç ile bölgeler arasındaki eşitsizlikler daha görünür hale gelir. Sanayisi gelişmiş, kamu hizmetleri işlevsel olan ve bu hizmetlere erişim imkanları daha kolay olan bölgeler az gelişmiş bölgelerdeki nüfusu kendilerine çekerler. Bunun sonucunda gelişmiş bölgelerin, altyapıları ne kadar iyi olsa da, karşılanacak göçlerin gelişmiş bölgelerin kapasitelerini aşmasıyla plansız kentleşme, gecekondulaşma, trafik problemi ve çevresel zararlar gibi sorunlar ortaya çıkmaya başlar. Bunun yanında, küçük şehirler de bazı itici faktörlere sahiptir. Bu faktörler zaman içinde değişiklik göstermiştir ve insanlar itici ve çekici

faktörlerin etkileriyle şehirlerarası göçler sırasında farklı sebeplerden ötürü Türkiye'nin farklı bölgelerine doğru göç etmişlerdir. Son yıllarda, göç sürecine ilişkin bu anlayış da değişmiş ve tersine göç eğilimleri veya kırsal alanlara ve küçük şehirlere geri dönme, zamanla vatandaşlar için tercih edilen seçenekler haline gelmiştir. Günümüzde halen büyük şehirlere göçler devam etse de, göç rotası yavaş yavaş küçük şehirlere doğru dönmeye başlamıştır. Bu olgu Türkiye'de göç dinamiklerinin zaman içinde nasıl değişime uğradığına dair önemli bir çerçeve sunmaktadır. Aynı zamanda, şehirlerarası göçler Cumhuriyet'in ilanında günümüze kadar gelen her dönemde yaşanmış, şehirlerde hem yapısal hem toplumsal anlamda değişikliğe sebep olmuştur ve buna bağlı olarak göç alan ve göç veren bölgelerde, göçün meydana getirdiği pozitif ve negatif yansımalar ortaya çıkmıştır.

Bu araştırmanın amacı göçün dönemlere göre değişkenlik gösteren itme ve çekme faktörlerinin incelenmesidir. Bu itme ve çekme faktörleri farklı sebeplerle insanları belli bölgelerden başka bölgelere itmiş veya çekmiştir. Böylece her dönemde gelişen siyasi, ekonomik ve sosyolojik olayların topluma yansımaları ile ilgili detaylı bir analiz yapılmış ve özellikle bu olayların göçleri nasıl şekillendirdiği ortaya konulmuştur. Türkiye örneğinde önceki dönemlerde, özellikle 20. yy.'da, Cumhuriyet dönemi ve sonrasında, itme ve çekme faktörleri detaylı olarak incelenmiş ve özellikle son zamanlarda, 2000 senesi ve sonrasında, ortaya çıkan yeni gelişmeler örneğin tersine göç politikaları, COVID-19 ve deprem gibi faktörler de göz önünde bulundurulunca, göçün sadece siyaset ve ekonomi odaklı değil aynı zamanda sosyolojik ve çevresel faktörlerle de tetiklendiği ortaya konulmuştur. Ayrıca, dönemsel olarak itme ve çekme faktörlerinin nasıl değişime uğradığı üzerine bir detaylı bir analiz yapılarak Türkiye Cumhuriyeti tarihinde meydana gelen olaylar ve bu olayların göçlerle olan bağlantısı incelenmiştir. Bu çalışma ile özellikle son zamanlarda farklı toplumsal olaylardan kaynaklanan göçlerin nasıl oluştuğu ve göçün meydana getirdiği yan etkilerin getirdiği problemler ortaya konulup, göçün sebepleri kadar sonuçlarının da şehirleşme ve toplum psikolojisi üzerinde nasıl bir etki oluşturduğu analiz edilmiştir.

Araştırma metodu olarak nitel yöntem kullanılmış, göç araştırmaları üzerinde yazılan hem Türkiye odaklı hem uluslararası göç teorilerini inceleyen kaynaklar ve bunun yanında haber kaynakları, göç ve iskan politikaları ile alakalı olan kanunlar ve maddeler, devlet kurumlarında ve bakanlıklarda göç üzerine yapılan projeler ve programlar kapsamlı bir biçimde incelenerek, Türkiye'deki göç süreci, göç politikaları ve çözüm önerileri üzerinde durulmuştur. Bu çalışmada, Türkiye'deki şehirlerarası göçleri etkileyen faktörlerin tarihsel değişimleri incelenmiştir. Göç sürecinin teorik yönü, şehirlerarası göçlerin itici ve çekici faktörleri, temel motivasyonlar ve sosyolojik faktörler ile göç sürecinin sonuçları ele alınacaktır. Son olarak, farklı dönemlere göre şehirlerarası göçün karşılaştırmalı bir analizi yapılarak, dönemsel farklılıklar ve benzerlikler ortaya konulacaktır.

Dönemler arası analiz yapılmasının amacı ve makalenin özgün katkısı geçmişte gerçekleşen göçlerin olumsuz etkilerini göz önünde bulundurarak, gelecekte oluşabilecek göç hareketlerinin oluşturabileceği itici faktörlerin önüne geçilmesi, günümüz tersine göç trendlerinin küçük şehirlerde

tekrardan itici faktör oluşturmaması, ve küçük şehirler ve kırsal bölgelerde girişim, yatırım oluşturularak bu bölgelerde kalkınma sağlanmasını kolay hale getirmektir. Bunlardan yola çıkarak, politika yapıcılar için bu çalışma ileride örnek teşkil edecektir ve bunun yanında göç hareketlerinin olumsuz etkilerinin önüne geçilebilmesi adına bir rehberlik sağlayacaktır.

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